

AN ANALYSIS, OF THE THESIS, IN THE FIELD OF LOGISTICS THAT FOUND AT THE YÖK THESIS CENTER AND AN ELABORATION OF THE LOGISTICS FIELD WITHIN THE SCOPE OF THE DEPARTMENT

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ABSTRACT

This research is a content analysis study that aims to reveal the interest in the postgraduate theses written in the field of Logistics through the YÖK National Thesis Center, which is the postgraduate thesis database in Turkey, and to reveal the corresponding knowledge. Within the scope of the research, a total of 1325 scientific theses were determined by examining 1001 master's and 324 doctoral theses. Since it was observed that the Logistics field was mostly realized in the Department of Business Administration, the study was also detailed in this sub-branch. Research in Turkey includes master's and doctoral thesis fields written in the field of Logistics, universities where the theses were made, and at the same time, the theses written in the field of business administration; It includes subject headings, methods, samples, sub-topics, distribution according to titles, distribution by gender, distribution of universities according to regions, type of university, distribution of institutes, languages in which the study was written, years in which the study was written, and the distribution of the studies according to the number of pages. This research shows the current perspective of Logistics, which has recently gained momentum in terms of its field of study in Turkey, and sheds light on the future studies of researchers who will find in the literature in the field of Logistics and makes some suggestions to them.

Keywords: Logistics, Department of Business Administration, Content analysis, YÖK national thesis center

INTRODUCTION

Logistics discipline, which includes the movement of human information and goods, is gradually expanding its boundaries (Dinçel, 2016). Basically, logistics is defined as a discipline that includes the application of fields of activity such as storage, packaging, order planning, service inventory of the services requested with an applicable accessibility (Dinçel, 2019). Logistics is also Dr. It has been expanded by Ömer Baybars Tek with a very sophisticated explanation as “to promise and keep one's word” (Tek, 2012). At this stage, it can be said that the promise and keeping promises of logistics express a wide spectrum together with business science within the scope of the business discipline that includes international trade. At this stage, it can be stated that logistics science is expected to expand in the academic framework.

Business disciplines, which are indispensable for academic units in the world, appear as an important discipline that mirrors the future (Williamson, 2005; Roetzal, 2019, Dinçel, 2022). Businesses, which are formed with the contributions of individuals who make up the society, can be introduced as passive creatures focused on the production of goods and services that continue their lives just like people (Dinçel, 2019). Business sciences have a

wide range of activities (Opatha, 2019). It has a structure that includes business functions and Logistics discipline. At this stage, it was seen that the studies on the field of logistics were handled within the framework of business science (Sharman, 1984; Bierwirth et al., 2019).

At this point, three main aims of this study can be mentioned. First, it tries to understand the interest of the authors in the theses written on the field of Logistics and sheds light on future studies by presenting a wide range of sub-branches. The second is to understand the orientation of the Department of Business Administration, which is the science most interested in the field of logistics, to logistics sub-branches and to provide foresight for future studies.

The third aim is to examine the stage of scientific production resources of logistics, which has gained a place in the sector with an important disciplinary distinction after the 2000s, within the framework of postgraduate theses.

METHOD

This research includes a content analysis method limited to thesis studies. Content analysis is a useful analysis technique in scanning the data and understanding the meanings in the data (Yıldırım ve Şimşek, 2016). Content analysis involves examining the observed content of any communication objectively, systematically and quantitatively (Berelson, 1952; Carpenter et al., 2012). Within the scope of the research, content analysis was carried out within the scope of YÖK National Thesis Center Database. In the first stage of the study, the theses that are thought to be related to Logistics were scanned with the keyword "Logistics" through detailed scanning and advanced searches on the <https://tez.yok.gov.tr/UlusalTezMerkezi/tarama.jsp> site. In the second stage, studies containing the keyword "Logistics" in the department of business administration were included. Within the scope of the research, firstly, whether it is open to access or not, the data that is not open to access are also included up to a certain stage. The study includes studies up to September 2022.

Among the scientific theses made in Turkey, 1325 theses containing the field of logistics and 414 theses with the keyword logistics related to the business department were found. Of these 1325 theses, 1001 are master's and 224 are doctoral dissertations.

FINDINGS

Findings are given below with sub-items.

Analysis of Thesis Areas on Logistics in Turkey

Thesis areas and rates (%) including the distribution of master's theses written in the field of Logistics in Turkey are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of Master's Theses Written in the Field of Logistics in Turkey

Thesis Type	Thesis Field	Number of Theses	%
Master 's Degree	Business Administration = Business Administration	415	41.46%
Master 's Degree	Industrial and Industrial Engineering = Industrial and Industrial Engineering	163	16.28%
Master 's Degree	Transportation = Transportation ; Business Administration = Business Administration	72	7.19%
Master 's Degree	Statistics = Statistics	61	6.09%
Master 's Degree	Transportation = Transportation	47	4.70%
Master 's Degree	Economics = Economics	25	2.50%
Master 's Degree	Education and Training = Education and Training	16	1.60%
Master 's Degree	Computer Engineering and Computer Science and Control = Computer Engineering and Computer Science and Control	14	1.40%
Master 's Degree	Biostatistics = Biostatistics,	12	1.20%
Master 's Degree	Econometrics = Econometrics,	12	1.20%
Master 's Degree	Economy = Economics ; Business Administration = Business Administration,	12	1.20%
Master 's Degree	Mathematics = Mathematics	9	0.90%
Master 's Degree	International Relations = International Relations	9	0.90%
Master 's Degree	Other	134	13.39%
Total		1001	100.00 %

Thesis areas and rates (%) including the distribution of doctoral theses written in the field of Logistics in Turkey are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Distribution of PhD Theses Written in the Field of Logistics in Turkey

Thesis Type	Thesis Field	Number of Theses	%
Doctorate	Business Administration = Business Administration	88	39.29%
Doctorate	Industrial and Industrial Engineering = Industrial and Industrial Engineering	26	11.61%
Doctorate	Statistics = Statistics	14	6.25%
Doctorate	Transportation = Transportation ; Business Administration = Business Administration	10	4.46%
Doctorate	Date = History	8	3,57%
Doctorate	Economics = Economics	7	3.13%
Doctorate	Education and Training = Education and Training	6	2.68%
Doctorate	Econometrics = Econometrics	4	1.79%
Doctorate	Economy = Economics ; Transportation = Transportation ; Business Administration = Business Administration	3	1.34%
Doctorate	Civil Engineering = Civil Engineering	3	1.34%
Doctorate	Medical Biology = Medical Biology	3	1.34%
Doctorate	Transportation = Transportation	3	1.34%
Doctorate	Other	49	21.88%
Total		224	100.00%

The distribution of theses written in the field of Logistics in Turkey according to universities and their rates (%) are given in Table 3.

Table 3: Distribution of Theses Written in the Field of Logistics in Turkey by Universities

University Name	Number of Theses	%
Dokuz Eylül University	108	8.15%
Marmara University	91	6.87%
İstanbul Teknik University	72	5.43%
Gazi University	60	4.53%
Istanbul University	51	3.85%
Yıldız Teknik University	45	3.40%
Istanbul Ticaret University	32	2.42%
Bahçeşehir University	24	1.81%
Selcuk University	22	1.66%
Okan University	22	1.66%
Akdeniz University	21	1.58%
Beykent University	20	1.51%
Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam University	20	1.51%
Maltepe University	20	1.51%
Yaşar University	20	1.51%
Other	697	52.60%
Total	1325	100.00 %

Analysis of Theses Written on Logistics in the Department of Business Administration in Turkey

The regions and numerical ratios (%) of the theses written on the field of Logistics in the Department of Business Administration in Turkey are given in Table 4.

Table 4: Distribution of Universities in Turkey with Theses Written on Logistics in the Department of Business Administration by Regions

Region	Number of Theses	%
Marmara	187	45.17%
Ege	85	20.53%
İç Anadolu	58	14.01%
Akdeniz	38	9.18%
Karadeniz	18	4.35%
Güneydoğu Anadolu	15	3.62%
Doğu Anadolu	13	3.14%
Total	414	100.00%

Table 5 shows the distribution of theses written in the field of Logistics in the Department of Business Administration in Turkey, according to the titles and number, and their rates (%).

Table 5: Distribution of Theses Written on Logistics in the Department of Business Administration in Turkey by Subject Headings

Subject Headings	Number of Theses	%
Logistics	118	28.50%
Supply Chain Management	42	10.14%
Outsourcing	34	8.21%
Reverse Logistics	27	6.52%
Global Competition	26	6.28%
in International Trade	22	5.31%
Cost	21	5.07%
Service Quality	15	3.62%
Marketing	15	3.62%
Customer Satisfaction	15	3.62%
Green Logistics	14	3.38%
Financial Ratio	11	2.66%
Other	54	13.04%
Total	414	100.00%

Table 6 shows the distribution of the theses written in the field of Logistics in the Department of Business Administration in Turkey according to the number of analysis techniques and their ratios (%).

Table 6: Distribution of Theses Written on Logistics in the Department of Business Administration in Turkey by Analysis Technique

Thesis Method	Number of Theses	%
Quantitative	229	55.31%
Qualitative	185	44.69%
Total	414	100.00%

The distribution and proportions (%) of the theses written in the field of Logistics in the Department of Business Administration in Turkey, depending on the sample topics, are given in Table 7.

Table 7: Sample Distribution of Theses Written on Logistics in the Department of Business Administration in Turkey

Sector	Number of Theses	%
Logistics	152	36.71%
Multi - Sector	131	31.64%
International Trade	25	6.04%
Marketing	17	4.11%
Finance	16	3.86%
Health	14	3.38%
Manufacturing	12	2.90%
Accounting	11	2.66%
Industry 4.0	10	2.42%
Other	26	6.28%
Total	414	100.00%

The distribution and proportions (%) of the theses written in the field of Logistics in the Department of Business Administration in Turkey according to the titles of the advisors are given in Table 8.

Table 8: Distribution of Supervisors of Theses Written on Logistics in the Department of Business Administration in Turkey by Titles

Consultant Title	Number of Theses	%
Prof. Dr.	119	28.74%
Assoc. Prof. Dr.	117	28.26%
Assist. Prof. Dr.	104	25.12%
Dr. Faculty Member	56	13.53%
Dr.	18	4.35%
Total	414	100.00%

Gender distributions and rates (%) of thesis writers written in the field of Logistics in the Department of Business Administration in Turkey are given in Table 9.

Table 9: Distribution of Thesis Authors Written About Logistics in the Department of Business Administration in Turkey by Gender

Gender	Number of Theses	%
Male	225	54.35%
Women	189	45.65%
Total	414	100.00%

The distribution and rates (%) of the theses written in the field of Logistics in the Department of Business Administration in Turkey according to the university types are given in Table 10.

Table 10: Distribution of Theses Written on Logistics in the Department of Business Administration in Turkey by University Types

University Type	Number of Theses	%
State University	282	68.12%
Private University	132	31.88%
Total	414	100.00%

The distribution and rates (%) of the theses written in the field of Logistics in the Department of Business Administration in Turkey according to the institutes are given in Table 11.

Table 11: Distribution of Theses Written on Logistics in the Department of Business Administration in Turkey by Institutes

Type of Institute	Number of Theses	%
Social Sciences Institute	354	85.51%
Institute of Marine Sciences and Engineering	9	2.17%
Postgraduate Education Graduate School	25	6.04%
Institute of Defense Sciences	6	1.45%
Graduate School of Natural and Applied Sciences	12	2.90%
Foreign Trade Institute	3	0.72%
Institute of Marine Sciences and Business Administration	4	0.97%
Graduate School of Educational Sciences	1	0.24%
Total	414	100.00%

CONCLUSION

The sector-based research level of the logistics discipline in the world is increasing day by day. At this stage, it is seen that logistics, which is the leverage of global trade, is the subject of qualified research. Postgraduate theses can be categorized in the relevant subject at this stage. In particular, it is important for the academic advisors to see how much the sub-disciplines of logistics are mentioned in their subject determination and orientation.

In the search carried out at the Higher Education Council National Thesis Center, 1325 theses containing the field of Logistics, among the scientific theses carried out in Turkey, and 414 theses with the keyword logistics related to the business department were found. Of these 1325 theses, 1001 are master's and 224 are doctoral dissertations.

Considering the distribution of theses written in the field of Logistics in Turkey according to universities, it was seen that among 1325 theses, 108 theses were written at Dokuz Eylül University with a rate of 8.15%. This is followed by Marmara University with 91 theses and 6.87%, Istanbul Technical University with 72 theses and 5.43%, and Gazi University with 60 theses with 4.53%.

When we look at the distribution of master's theses written in the field of Logistics in Turkey, it is seen that 41.46% were carried out in the field of Business Administration, 16.28% in the field of Industrial and Industrial Engineering, 7.19% in the field of Transportation and 6.09% in the field of Statistics. seen.

Considering the distribution of doctoral theses written in the field of Logistics in Turkey, it was determined that 39.29% were carried out in the field of Business Administration, 11.61% in the field of Industrial and Industrial Engineering, and 6.25% in the field of Statistics.

Accordingly, the field of Business Administration has attracted attention as a field of study in the discipline of Logistics, and therefore, research has been carried out on 414 theses on the field of logistics sub-discipline carried out in the field of business.

When we look at the distribution of the universities in Turkey, where the theses written in the field of Business Administration are located, according to the regions, it is seen that the Marmara Region is in the first place with 187 theses and the corresponding 45.17%. In the second place is the Aegean Region with 85 theses, which corresponds to 20.53%, in the third place is the Central Anatolia Region with 58 theses, which corresponds to 14.01%, and in the fourth place is the Mediterranean Region, which corresponds to 9.18% with 38 theses. , the Black Sea Region is in the fifth place with 18 theses, corresponding to 4.35%, the Southeastern Anatolia Region is in the sixth place with 15 theses, corresponding to 3.62%, and the Eastern Anatolia Region is in the last place, corresponding to 13 theses with a rate of 3.14%. It has been observed that the Anatolian region is located.

When the distribution of the theses written in the field of Logistics in the Department of Business Administration in Turkey according to the titles is examined, it is seen that the title of "Logistics" takes the first place with a rate of 28.50%, with 118 theses out of 414 theses. It is seen that the title "Supply Chain Management" ranks second with 42 theses, corresponding to 10.14%, followed by titles such as "Outsourcing, Reverse Logistics, Global Competition, Logistics in International Trade, Cost".

It has been observed that 229 of the 414 theses related to the analysis sample distribution of the theses written in the field of Business Administration in Turkey were realized with the Quantitative method with a rate of 55.31%, while 185 theses were realized with the Qualitative method with a rate of 44.69%.

Considering the sample distribution of 144 theses written in the field of Business Administration in Turkey, "Logistics" with 152 theses corresponding to 36.71%, and "Multi-sector" with 131 theses corresponding to 31.64% come to the fore.

Considering the distribution of the theses written in the field of Business Administration in Turkey according to the titles of their advisors, the 110 theses out of 414 theses correspond to "Prof.Dr. "Associate Prof.Dr." with a rate of 28.26% corresponding to 117 theses, "Assistant Prof.Dr." with a rate of 25.12% corresponding to 104 theses, 13.53% corresponding to 56 theses "Dr. Faculty Member" with a ratio of 4.35% and "Dr. Lecturer" distribution was seen.

When we look at the distribution of thesis writers on Logistics in the Department of Business Administration by gender, it is seen that 225 theses, which corresponds to 54.35% of 414 theses, were written by men. It was determined that 189 theses, corresponding to 45.65%, were written by women.

When we look at the distribution of the theses written in the field of Business Administration in Turkey according to the types of universities where they are written, it is observed that 68.12% corresponding to 282 theses were written at State University and 31.88% corresponding to 132 theses were written at Foundation Universities.

When the distribution of the theses written in the field of Logistics in the Department of Business Administration in Turkey according to the institutes is examined, it is seen that the theses were written in the institute of social sciences with a rate of 85.51%, corresponding to 354 out of 414 theses.

In general, the above-mentioned determinations show the current status of master's and doctoral theses in the field of Logistics in Turkey. This situation guides scientists, thesis advisors, thesis writers, article and paper writers, and project coordinators in the public world.

REFERENCES

- Berelson, B. (1952). Content analysis in communication research.
- Bierwirth, C., Kirschstein, T., & Sackmann, D. (2019). Logistics Management. *Cham: Springer International Publishing (Lecture Notes in Logistics)*.
- Dinçel, S. (2014). Lojistik sektöründe girişimcilik; Örnek bir firma incelemesi. İstanbul Aydın Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü İşletme Anabilim Dalı İşletme Yönetimi Bilim Dalı, 65.
- Dinçel, S. (2016). *Lojistik yönetimi ve girişimcilik*. Hiperlink eğit. ilet. yay. san. tic. ve ltd. sti..
- Dinçel, S. (2019). *Girişimcilik*. Togan.
- Dinçel, S. (2019). İşletme Yönetimi ve Lojistik. Togan.
- Dinçel, S. (2022). Social Responsibility in Businesses: An Overview of Turkish Logistics Sector. Ö. K. Tüfekci & L. Akbaş (Ed.), *Global Social Science Research: Theoretical and Empirical Evaluations* (p. 63-82). Klaipeda: SRA Academic Publishing
- <http://yok.tez.gov.tr>
- Marangoz, M., Yeşildağ, B., & Saltik, İ. A. (2012). E-ticaret işletmelerinin web ve sosyal ağ sitelerinin içerik analizi yöntemiyle incelenmesi. *Journal of Internet Applications and Management*, 3(2), 53-78.

Opatha, H. H. D. N. P. (2019). Sustainable human resource management. *Sri Lanka: Author.*

Roetzel, P. G. (2019). Information overload in the information age: a review of the literature from business administration, business psychology, and related disciplines with a bibliometric approach and framework development. *Business research, 12*(2), 479-522.

Sharman, G. (1984). The rediscovery of logistics. *Harvard business review, 62*(5).

Tek, Ö. B., & Karaduman, İ. (2012). Lojistik Yönetimi. *İstanbul: İhlas Gazetecilik AŞ, 5*, 254.

Williamson, O. E. (2005). Transaction cost economics and business administration. *Scandinavian journal of Management, 21*(1), 19-40.